

Synthesis of 3,5-Dimethyl-4-(substituted sulfonamidobenzene azo, *p*-Sulfophenyl and *p*-Sulfonaphthyl azo) pyrazoles and Evaluation of their Antibacterial Properties

P. S. FERNANDES, (MISS) BHATE SANDHYA, (MISS) PHILIP GITA and V. V. NADKARNY

Nadkarny-Sacasa Research Laboratory, St. Xavier's College, Bombay-1

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2,4-Diketo pentane was coupled with few of the diazotised sulfonamide bases, sulfanilic acid and naphthionic acid to yield 2,4-diketo-3-(aryl sulfonamido benzene azo) pentane. The azo compounds were condensed with hydrazine (98-100%) and hydrochlorides of phenyl hydrazine, tolyl hydrazine, *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine to yield 3,5-dimethyl-4-(substituted sulfonamidobenzene azo) pyrazoles and 3,5-dimethyl-4(*p*-sulfophenyl azo and *p*-sulfonaphthyl azo) pyrazoles. All these derivatives have been screened for antibacterial activity.

GR^{EAT} importance is being given to pyrazole derivatives due to their use in therapeutics¹⁻⁷. Some of the pyrazole derivatives have been found to have anticancer properties^{8,9}. Pyrazoles having sulfonamide moiety attached at different positions have been synthesised and reported to be active against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*¹⁰⁻¹². Recently some pyrazole derivatives having aryl groups at 3- and 5-position have been synthesised and tested against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*¹³. Therefore it was thought of interest to synthesise some 3,5-dimethyl pyrazoles having an azo grouping, sulfonamide and sulfonic acid moiety and study their antibacterial properties.

Substituted sulfonamidobenzene azo, benzene azo-4-sulfonic acid and naphthalene azo-4-sulfonic acid derivatives of 2,4-diketo pentane (acetyl acetone) were prepared by coupling the β -ketone with diazotised sulfonamido bases, sulfanilic acid and naphthionic acid (St. Ia and Ib) in the presence of sodium acetate¹⁷. The azo derivatives of 2,4-diketo pentane obtained was then reacted with four carbonyl reagents, hydrazine hydrate (98-100%), phenylhydrazine hydrochloride, *p*-tolyl hydrazine hydrochloride and 4-nitrophenyl hydrazine hydrochloride to furnish corresponding N-substituted 3,5-dimethyl-4-(substituted aryl sulfonamido benzene azo) pyrazoles of the type IIa N-substituted 3,5-dimethyl-4-(*p*-sulfophenyl azo and *p*-sulfonaphthyl azo) pyrazoles of the type IIb.

Experimental

The sulfonamides required for the work were prepared by standard methods¹⁴⁻¹⁶. The azo compounds from acetyl acetone (Table 1) were obtained in 48-75% yield by the method reported earlier¹⁷. The melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

3,5-Dimethyl-4-(substituted sulfonamidobenzene azo) pyrazoles (Table 2):

The azo compounds (0.001 mole) obtained as above in glacial acetic acid and hydrazine hydrate (98-100%, 0.001 mole) was refluxed for 8-10 hr. The solution was cooled and allowed to stand overnight. The crystalline product separated was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

Pyrazoles from phenylhydrazine, *p*-tolylhydrazine and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine hydrochlorides were prepared according to the method reported¹³; yields ranging from 46-75%.

3,5-Dimethyl-4(*p*-sulfophenyl azo and *p*-sulfonaphthyl azo) pyrazoles, (Table 3):

Sulfanilic acid and naphthionic acid (0.05 mole) were diazotised¹⁸ and coupled with an ice cold solution

TABLE 1—2,4-DIKETO-(SUBSTITUTED SULFONAMIDOBENZENE AZO) PENTANE (IA)

S.No.	R	M.P. °C	<i>B. subtilis</i>		<i>Stap. aureus</i>		<i>S. typhi</i>		<i>E. coli</i>		<i>Ps.aeruginosa</i>		<i>Shi.flexneri</i>	
			2 mg	3 mg	2 mg	3 mg	2 mg	3 mg	2 mg	3 mg	2 mg	3 mg	2 mg	3 mg
1.	H	216	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
2.	-CH ₂ COOH	191-2	±	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
3.	-C ₆ H ₅	171	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
4.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	174	+	+	±	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
5.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	168	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
6.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	197	+	+	+	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	+	+
7.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	177	—	—	±	±	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
8.	Naphthyl	159	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

(—) = no inhibition ; (±) = partial inhibition ; (+) = complete inhibition.
The elemental analysis of all the compounds (C, H, N, S) were found to be correct.

TABLE 2—3,5-DIMETHYL-4(SUBSTITUTED SULFONAMIDOBENZENE AZO) PYRAZOLES (IIA)

S.No.	R	R ₂	M.P. °C	<i>B. subtilis</i>		<i>Staph.aureus</i>		<i>S. typhi</i>		<i>E. coli</i>		<i>P.aeruginosa</i>		<i>Shi.flexneri</i>	
				2 mg	3 mg	2 mg	3 mg	2 mg	3 mg	2 mg	3 mg	2 mg	3 mg	2 mg	3 mg
9.	H	H	265	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
10.	-CH ₂ COOH	„	260	+	+	+	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	+	+
11.	-C ₆ H ₅	„	230	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
12.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	„	208	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
13.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	„	220	+	+	+	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	+	+
14.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	„	200	±	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	±	+	—	—
15.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	„	205	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
16.	Naphthyl	„	211	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
17.	H	-C ₆ H ₅	192	—	—	—	—	+	+	—	—	—	—	—	—
18.	-CH ₂ COOH	„	251	—	+	—	—	+	+	—	±	—	±	+	+
19.	-C ₆ H ₅	„	206	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
20.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	„	235	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
21.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	„	261	+	+	+	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
22.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	„	243	±	+	±	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
23.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	„	218	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
24.	Naphthyl	„	203	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
25.	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	218	+	+	+	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	+	+
26.	-CH ₂ COOH	„	239	±	+	—	—	±	+	—	—	—	—	±	+
27.	-C ₆ H ₅	„	240	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
28.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	„	252	+	+	+	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
29.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	„	272	+	+	+	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
30.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	„	263	+	+	+	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
31.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	„	231	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
32.	Naphthyl	„	221	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
33.	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	212	—	—	±	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
34.	-CH ₂ COOH	„	238	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
35.	-C ₆ H ₅	„	268	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
36.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	„	259	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
37.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	„	286	+	+	+	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	+	+
38.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	„	213	±	+	±	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
39.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	„	247	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
40.	Naphthyl	„	246	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

(—) = no inhibition ; (±) = partial inhibition ; (+) = complete inhibition.
The elemental analysis of all the compounds (C, H, N, S) were found to be correct.

of acetyl acetone (0.05 mole) in acetone containing sodium acetate. The reaction mixture was stirred for 10 min and allowed to stand at room temperature for 1 hr. 2,4-Diketo-3-(*p*-sulfophenylazo) pentane was separated as sodium salt by the addition of sodium chloride. It was crystallised from brine solution. Whereas 2,4-Diketo-3-(*p*-sulfonaphthyl azo) pentane was separated, filtered and crystallised from alcohol. Yield 69–72%. The pyrazole from hydrazine hydrate,

phenyl hydrazine, *p*-tolyl hydrazine, and *p*-nitrophenyl hydrazine were prepared by the above method. Whereas 3,5-dimethyl-4-(*p*-sulfophenylazo) pyrazole was isolated as the sodium salt.

Screening for antibacterial activity : The compounds listed in Tables 1–3 have been evaluated for their antibacterial activity. The test organisms employed were as follows : *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus*

TABLE 3—2,4-DIKETO-3 (*p*-SULFOPHENYL AZO AND NAPHTHYL AZO) PENTANE (Ib); 3,5-DIMETHYL-4 (*p*-SULFOPHENYL AZO AND *p*-SULFONAPHTHYLAZO) PYRAZOLES (IIb)

S.No.	R ₁	R ₂	M.P. °C	<i>B. subtilis</i>		<i>Staph. aureus</i>		<i>S. typhi</i>		<i>E. coli</i>		<i>Ps.aeruginosa</i>		<i>Shi.flexneri</i>	
				2 mg	3 mg	2 mg	3 mg	2 mg	3 mg	2 mg	3 mg	2 mg	3 mg	2 mg	3 mg
41.	<i>p</i> -SO ₃ HC ₆ H ₄	—	does not melt	—	—	—	—	+	+	—	—	—	—	—	—
42.	<i>p</i> -SO ₃ HC ₁₀ H ₆	—	328 (decomp)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
43.	<i>p</i> -SO ₃ NaC ₆ H ₄	H	—	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
44.	<i>p</i> -SO ₃ HC ₁₀ H ₆	H	305 (decomp)	+	+	+	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	+	+
45.	<i>p</i> -SO ₃ HC ₆ H ₄	-C ₆ H ₅	211	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
46.	<i>p</i> -SO ₃ HC ₁₀ H ₆	-C ₆ H ₅	250	—	—	—	—	+	+	+	+	—	—	—	—
47.	<i>p</i> -SO ₃ HC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	280 (decomp)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
48.	<i>p</i> -SO ₃ HC ₁₀ H ₆	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	310 (decomp)	+	+	+	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	+	+
49.	<i>p</i> -SO ₃ HC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	261	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
50.	<i>p</i> -SO ₃ HC ₁₀ H ₆	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	296	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	+	+

(-) = no inhibition; (±) = partial inhibition; (+) = complete inhibition. The elemental analysis of all the compounds (C, H, N, S) were found to be correct.

aureus, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Shigella flexneri*. The antibacterial activity of the compounds was tested by ditch plate technique¹⁹, using the concentration levels 200 µg, 1 mg, 2 mg and 3 mg per ml.

The compound Nos. 43, 45, 47, 49 showed complete inhibition of all the organisms employed at all concentration levels. Compd. Nos. 44 and 48 showed partial inhibition of *B. subtilis*, *Staph. aureus* and *Shig. flexneri*, whereas comp No. 46 partially inhibited the growth of *S. typhi* and *E. coli* at the concentration level of 1 mg/ml. All the other compounds were found to be inactive at the concentration levels of 200 µg and 1 mg per ml. The results of antibacterial activity at the concentration levels of 2 mg and 3 mg per ml were depicted in Tables 1-3

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References

1. S. RICH and J. G. HORSFAU, *Phytopathology*, 1952, 42, 457.
2. E. C. HERBMAN and J. GRABLICKS, *Cancer Chemotherapy Reports*, 1961, 14, 85.
3. W. DYMEK, B. JANIK and O. SAMSON, *Acta. Polon. Pharm.*, 1964, 21, 211; *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, 62, 1048^o.
4. E. L. ANDERSON, J. E. CASEY, L. O. GREENE, J. J. JAFFERTY and H. E. REIFF, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, 1, 259.
5. R. HIRSCHMANN, N. G. STEINBERG, E. F. SCHOENEWALDT, W. J. PALWEDA and MAX. TISOHLER, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, 1, 352.
6. J. B. WRIGHT, W. E. DULIN and J. H. MARKILLIE, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, 7, 102.
7. R. E. ORTH, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1968, 57, 537.
8. W. WILSON and N. BOTTIGLIERI, *Cancer Chemotherapy*, 1962, 21, 137.
9. C. W. NOELL and C. C. CHENG, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, 12, 545.
10. I. I. GRANDBERG, WEI-PI TING and A. N. KOST, *Zhur Obshch. Khim.*, 1961, 31, 2311.
11. C. ALBERTI and C. BREGONZIO, *Framaco. (Pavia)Ed. d. Sci.*, 1961, 16, 540.
12. C. ALBERTI and C. TIRONI, *Framaco, (Pavia) Ed. Sci.*, 1967, 22, 58.
13. G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 351.
14. G. L. WEBSTER and L. D. POWERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 1553.
15. H. BAUER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 613.
16. R. O. ROBLIN, J. H. WILLIAMS, P. S. WINNEK and J. P. ENGLISH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1999.
17. P. S. FERNANDES, V. V. NADKARNY, G. A. JABBAR and R. P. JANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 840.
18. A. I. VOGEL, "Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd Ed., Longmans, 1971, p. 1006.
19. C. H. COLLINS and P. M. LYNE, "Microbiological Methods", 3rd Ed. Butterworths, London, 1970, p. 424.